

Career Arcs Phase 2 Interview script

Short version:

1. Please describe your background and education
2. Please describe three situations in which you did something that enabled you to grow in your career.
3. What factors had the greatest influence in shaping your path to an RCD role?
4. What factors had (or would have) the greatest influence in a decision to take your career in another direction?
5. What risks did you take in your career and how did they impact your career journey/arc/trajectory?
6. Where do you see yourself in five to ten years, within the context of RCD?

Long version (take notes here):

1) Get background of individual

- Probably start with Formal education (most comfortable)
- Experiences in school and work
- Did personal priorities ever play a role in your career?
 - Personal constraints - How can we ask this? What made your experience unique?
- **“Is there anything about the way you grew up that influenced your career?”**
 - **Demographic factors; age, gender, race, (socio-economic background??, parents’ background??)**
 - **How do you think any of this shaped your expectations, and ultimate career path?**
- **What kind of resources, connections, and community were you able to draw upon as you started your career, and over time as you have made career choices?**

2) I want you to think of three specific situations in which you did something that enabled you to grow in your career.

- What were the general circumstances leading up to this situation? Were there specific challenges that you encountered, and if so, how did these hinder or ultimately benefit your career?
- Tell me exactly what you did.
- Why (or how) were those actions so helpful?
- When did this happen? [*make a timeline of events for interviewee*]

3) What factors had the greatest influence in shaping your path to an RCD role?

- List these factors
- Order these factors
- What factors have you seen in your career that enable an RCD professional to grow in their career?
[possibly qualify to “...in your type of institution” or “in your institution”]
- Are there other factors like this you have seen in your co-workers’ careers?
- What are the primary qualities you would cite when you are competing for a promotion, a new position, etc.

4a) What factor do you think will have the greatest influence on your path, looking ahead?

4b) What factors had (or would have) the greatest influence in a decision to take your career in another direction?

5) What risks did you take in your career and how did they impact your career journey/arc/trajectory?

- What was the nature of the risk?
- How did you feel at the time, and in retrospect?

6) Where do you see yourself in five to ten years, within the context of RCD?